

The Dialectic of Paradox: Abortion and the Death of Collective Thought

by Francesco Freschi

1. Dialogue with Paradox

There are many opinions regarding pregnancy and what occurs during the first nine months of gestation. Some argue that a baby becomes a baby only once the brain is fully developed; others maintain that before three months it cannot be considered a “person.” A frequently repeated claim summarizes these positions: “*it is just a clump of cells.*”

First, it is scientifically established that even after birth the process of development is not complete and that the brain is not yet fully formed.¹ Consequently, it would be inconsistent to regard only those individuals who have completed brain development as “children.”

Second, there is a lack of consistency among different legal systems. In Italy, abortion is permitted during the first three months of pregnancy, whereas in other countries the legal limit varies. This suggests that human life begins at different moments depending on national boundaries. To claim that a “clump of cells” can suddenly become a human being appears to rely on a magical transformation: at one moment there is merely an “organic aggregation,” and at the next a person endowed with inviolable rights. In this view, such cells would become a “human person” by virtue of an arbitrary decision. One may then ask whether opinion has come to function as a new form of science.

Human dignity cannot be reduced to the presence of a particular bodily organ, nor to a specific moment within an overall developmental process, which is intrinsically continuous and unique. As the eminent French geneticist Jérôme Lejeune observed, this reality is human life from its beginning. One cannot coherently separate—as though they were distinct subjects—the fetus from the child, the adolescent from the young adult, or the adult from the elderly person; all are stages within the same process of human development.

The initial claims therefore constitute a paradox that reflects a widespread pattern of contemporary thinking on this issue.

2. What Is Abortion, Really?

In order to understand what abortion is, it is necessary to clarify when human life begins. At this level, the concept of human life is not philosophical but scientific. Since human beings are living organisms, biology must provide the relevant answer.

In 2021, a study² conducted by American researcher Steven Andrew Jacobs of the University of Chicago surveyed more than 5,577 biologists. Many of the respondents did not identify as religious or pro-life. When asked, from a biological perspective, “When does human life begin?”, 97% of those surveyed (5,337 out of 5,577) answered: “at fertilization.”

¹ Stiles, J., & Jernigan, T. L. (2010). *The Basics of Brain Development*. *Neuropsychology Review*, 20(4), 327–348.

“The human brain at birth is still very much a work in progress, with structural and functional development continuing for many years” (Stiles & Jernigan, 2010, p. 327).

² Jacobs, Steven Andrew. 2021. “The Scientific Consensus on When a Human’s Life Begins.” *Issues in Law & Medicine*.

Fertilization marks the beginning of the continuous process we call life; prior to this event, there is no human being. The social concept of personhood cannot be separated from the physical existence and biological reality of the individual. Otherwise, the term “person” risks becoming a dangerous and arbitrary designation—one that may be removed at will and ultimately used against the individual to whom it is applied. Such a move would open the door to discrimination between those deemed worthy of respect and those who may be deprived of their dignity.

In this sense, together with Gianna Jessen—one of the few known survivors of a voluntary saline abortion and now a pro-life activist—we can affirm that abortion destroys a developing human person by eliminating an original and unique DNA,³ within which fundamental personal characteristics are already present. Therefore, in all relevant respects, induced abortion constitutes the killing of an unborn person.

Today, Gianna Jessen advocates for the defense of innocent human beings who, like her, are at risk of being killed. There are already hundreds of thousands of women and men who could have profoundly changed our lives and our society but were never born.

3. The Death of Collective Thought

The transition of voluntary abortion from a crime to a perceived right, together with the widespread absence of critical reflection among large segments of the population, points to a progressive erosion of thought—one increasingly shaped by media influence and social conformity.

Voluntary abortion is the outcome of a specific socio-philosophical trajectory that elevates individual freedom as the sole foundation of moral action: a self-determining freedom whose limits remain undefined. Yet freedom cannot exist apart from truth. Its proper aim is the authentic realization of the human subject, which cannot be achieved without a sound ethical and anthropological understanding of the person. Freedom is not ordered toward the performance of evil, but toward the pursuit of the good; otherwise, it ultimately results in self-destruction.

In this context, it is mistakenly assumed that the moral value of actions does not lie in the actions themselves, but solely in the criterion of free choice: *I am free; therefore, I may do whatever I wish*. In this way, freedom is increasingly distorted into the individual’s will to impose itself. However, no act of choice can morally justify murder.

Moreover, it should be noted that the perception—cultural rather than strictly legal—of abortion as a right signals a profound decline in democratic understanding. Democracy is founded on respect for minorities and for all members of the political community. Why, then, does this principle fail to apply to those who are already among us, yet have not been born?

As previously noted, when rationality and truth are abandoned in favor of the mere principle of majority rule, society risks paving the way for a new form of authoritarianism. Such authoritarianism rests on a flawed anthropological conception and gives rise to a majority of tyrants prepared to “create” their own truth and impose it as an ideological doctrine.

This death of collective thought reveals a deep moral fragility within contemporary society, one that extends into political and economic spheres as well. Although the specific issues may differ, the same underlying values and methods persist. The result is what can reasonably be described as the greatest massacre of innocents of the twenty-first century - presented as a necessary good and as an “acquired right”.

³ Alberts, B. et al. (2022). *Molecular Biology of the Cell*. New York: Norton & Company. “The fertilized egg contains the complete genetic instructions necessary to direct the development of a complex organism”.

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